

ISic0787

I.Sicily inscription 0787

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Necropolis at the Orti della Maddalena

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale
interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3580

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR078344

1. D (is) M (anibus)
2. Ti (berius) Cl (adius) Claudianus
3. vix (it) ann (is) XIII
4. Cl (adius) Theseus pater
5. filio dulcissimo.

Edition: PHI313654

1. D (is) □ M (anibus) □
2. Ti (berius) □ Cl (adius) Claudianus
3. vix (it) □ ann (is) □ XIII.
4. Cl (adius) □ Theseus □ pater
5. filio □ dulcissimo.
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175708

EDR 078344

EDCS 14805805

PHI 313654

Bibliography

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